

A Class of Lie-admissible Algebras

Qihui Mo, Xiangui Zhao and Qingnian Pan

(Department of Mathematics, Huizhou University Huizhou 516007, P. R. China)

E-mail: scnuhuashimomo@126.com, xiangui.zhao@foxmail.com, pqn@hzu.edu.cn

Abstract: In this paper, we study nonassociative algebras which satisfy the following identities: $(xy)z = (yx)z, x(yz) = x(zy)$. These algebras are Lie-admissible algebras i.e., they become Lie algebras under the commutator $[f, g] = fg - gf$. We obtain a nonassociative Gröbner-Shirshov basis for the free algebra $LA(X)$ with a generating set X of the above variety. As an application, we get a monomial basis for $LA(X)$. We also give a characterization of the elements of $S(X)$ among the elements of $LA(X)$, where $S(X)$ is the Lie subalgebra, generated by X , of $LA(X)$.

Key Words: Nonassociative algebra, Lie admissible algebra, Gröbner-Shirshov basis.

AMS(2010): 17D25, 13P10, 16S15.

§1. Introduction

In 1948, A. A. Albert introduced a new family of (nonassociative) algebras whose commutator algebras are Lie algebras [1]. These algebras are called Lie-admissible algebras, and they arise naturally in various areas of mathematics and mathematical physics such as differential geometry of affine connections on Lie groups. Examples include associative algebras, pre-Lie algebras and so on.

Let $k\langle X \rangle$ be the free associative algebra generated by X . It is well known that the Lie subalgebra, generated X , of $k\langle X \rangle$ is a free Lie algebra (see for example [6]). Friedrichs [15] has given a characterization of Lie elements among the set of noncommutative polynomials. A proof of characterization theorem was also given by Magnus [18], who refers to other proofs by P. M. Cohn and D. Finkelstein. Later, two short proofs of the characterization theorem were given by R. C. Lyndon [17] and A. I. Shirshov [21], respectively.

Pre-Lie algebras arise in many areas of mathematics and physics. As was pointed out by D. Burde [8], these algebras first appeared in a paper by A. Cayley in 1896 (see [9]). Survey [8] contains detailed discussion of the origin, theory and applications of pre-Lie algebras in geometry and physics together with an extensive bibliography. Free pre-Lie algebras had already

¹Supported by the NNSF of China (Nos. 11401246; 11426112; 11501237), the NSF of Guangdong Province (Nos. 2014A030310087; 2014A030310119; 2016A030310099), the Outstanding Young Teacher Training Program in Guangdong Universities (No. YQ2015155), the Research Fund for the Doctoral Program of Huizhou University (Nos. C513.0210; C513.0209; 2015JB021) and the Scientific Research Innovation Team Project of Huizhou University (hzuxl201523).

²Received May 25, 2017, Accepted November 15, 2017.

been studied as early as 1981 by Agrachev and Gamkrelidze [2]. They gave a construction of monomial bases for free pre-Lie algebras. Segal [20] in 1994 gave an explicit basis (called good words in [20]) for a free pre-Lie algebra and applied it for the PBW-type theorem for the universal pre-Lie enveloping algebra of a Lie algebra. Linear bases of free pre-Lie algebras were also studied in [3, 10, 11, 14, 25]. As a special case of Segal's latter result, the Lie subalgebra, generated by X , of the free pre-Lie algebra with generating set X is also free. Independently, this result was also proved by A. Dzhumadil'daev and C. Löfwall [14]. M. Markl [19] gave a simple characterization of Lie elements in free pre-Lie algebras as elements of the kernel of a map between spaces of trees.

Gröbner bases and Gröbner-Shirshov bases were invented independently by A.I. Shirshov for ideals of free (commutative, anti-commutative) non-associative algebras [22, 24], free Lie algebras [23, 24] and implicitly free associative algebras [23, 24] (see also [4, 5, 12, 13]), by H. Hironaka [16] for ideals of the power series algebras (both formal and convergent), and by B. Buchberger [7] for ideals of the polynomial algebras.

In this paper, we study a class of Lie-admissible algebras. These algebras are nonassociative algebras which satisfy the following identities: $(xy)z = (yx)z, x(yz) = x(zy)$. Let $LA(X)$ be the free algebra with a generating set X of the above variety. We obtain a nonassociative Gröbner-Shirshov basis for the free algebra $LA(X)$. Using the Composition-Diamond lemma of nonassociative algebras, we get a monomial basis for $LA(X)$. Let $S(X)$ be the Lie subalgebra, generated by X , of $LA(X)$. We get a linear basis of $S(X)$. As a corollary, we show that $S(X)$ is not a free Lie algebra when the cardinality of X is greater than 1. We also give a characterization of the elements of $S(X)$ among the elements of $LA(X)$. For the completeness of this paper, we formulate the Composition-Diamond lemma for free nonassociative algebras in Section 2.

§2. Composition-Diamond Lemma for Nonassociative Algebras

Let X be a well ordered set. Each letter $x \in X$ is a nonassociative word of degree 1. Suppose that u and v are nonassociative words of degrees m and n respectively. Then uv is a nonassociative word of degree $m + n$. Denoted by $|uv|$ the degree of uv , by X^* the set of all associative words on X and by X^{**} the set of all nonassociative word on X . If $u = (p(v)q)$, where $p, q \in X^*, u, v \in X^{**}$, then v is called a subword of u . Denote u by $u|_v$, if this is the case.

The set X^{**} can be ordered by the following way: $u > v$ if either

- (1) $|u| > |v|$; or
- (2) $|u| = |v|$ and $u = u_1u_2, v = v_1v_2$, and either
 - (2a) $u_1 > v_1$; or
 - (2b) $u_1 = v_1$ and $u_2 > v_2$.

This ordering is called degree lexicographical ordering and used throughout this paper.

Let k be a field and $M(X)$ be the free nonassociative algebra over k , generated by X . Then

each nonzero element $f \in M(X)$ can be presented as

$$f = \alpha \bar{f} + \sum_i \alpha_i u_i,$$

where $\bar{f} > u_i$, $\alpha, \alpha_i \in k$, $\alpha \neq 0$, $u_i \in X^{**}$. Then \bar{f} , α are called the leading term and leading coefficient of f respectively and f is called monic if $\alpha = 1$. Denote by $d(f)$ the degree of f , which is defined by $d(f) = |\bar{f}|$.

Let $S \subset M(X)$ be a set of monic polynomials, $s \in S$ and $u \in X^{**}$. We define S -word $(u)_s$ in a recursive way:

- (i) $(s)_s = s$ is an S -word of s -length 1;
- (ii) If $(u)_s$ is an S -word of s -length k and v is a nonassociative word of degree l , then

$$(u)_s v \quad \text{and} \quad v(u)_s$$

are S -words of s -length $k + l$.

Note that for any S -word $(u)_s = (asb)$, where $a, b \in X^*$, we have $\overline{(asb)} = (a(\bar{s})b)$.

Let f, g be monic polynomials in $M(X)$. Suppose that there exist $a, b \in X^*$ such that $\bar{f} = (a(\bar{g})b)$. Then we define the composition of inclusion

$$(f, g)_{\bar{f}} = f - (agb).$$

The composition $(f, g)_{\bar{f}}$ is called trivial modulo (S, \bar{f}) , if

$$(f, g)_{\bar{f}} = \sum_i \alpha_i (a_i s_i b_i)$$

where each $\alpha_i \in k$, $a_i, b_i \in X^*$, $s_i \in S$, $(a_i s_i b_i)$ an S -word and $(a_i(\bar{s}_i)b_i) < \bar{f}$. If this is the case, then we write $(f, g)_{\bar{f}} \equiv 0 \pmod{(S, \bar{f})}$. In general, for $p, q \in M(X)$ and $w \in X^{**}$, we write

$$p \equiv q \pmod{(S, w)}$$

which means that $p - q = \sum \alpha_i (a_i s_i b_i)$, where each $\alpha_i \in k$, $a_i, b_i \in X^*$, $s_i \in S$, $(a_i s_i b_i)$ an S -word and $(a_i(\bar{s}_i)b_i) < w$.

Definition 2.1 ([22,24]) *Let $S \subset M(X)$ be a nonempty set of monic polynomials and the ordering $>$ defined as before. Then S is called a Gröbner-Shirshov basis in $M(X)$ if any composition $(f, g)_{\bar{f}}$ with $f, g \in S$ is trivial modulo (S, \bar{f}) , i.e., $(f, g)_{\bar{f}} \equiv 0 \pmod{(S, \bar{f})}$.*

Theorem 2.2 ([22,24]) (Composition-Diamond lemma for nonassociative algebras) *Let $S \subset M(X)$ be a nonempty set of monic polynomials, $Id(S)$ the ideal of $M(X)$ generated by S and the ordering $>$ on X^{**} defined as before. Then the following statements are equivalent:*

- (i) S is a Gröbner-Shirshov basis in $M(X)$;
- (ii) $f \in Id(S) \Rightarrow \bar{f} = (a(\bar{s})b)$ for some $s \in S$ and $a, b \in X^*$, where (asb) is an S -word;

(iii) $Irr(S) = \{u \in X^{**} | u \neq (a(\bar{s})b) \ a, b \in X^*, \ s \in S \text{ and } (asb) \text{ is an } S\text{-word}\}$ is a linear basis of the algebra $M(X|S) = M(X)/Id(S)$.

§3. A Nonassociative Gröbner-Shirshov Basis for the Algebra $LA(X)$

Let \mathcal{LA} be the variety of nonassociative algebras which satisfy the following identities: $(xy)z = (yx)z, x(yz) = x(zx)$. Let $LA(X)$ be the free algebra with a generating set X of the variety \mathcal{LA} . It's clear that the free algebra $LA(X)$ is isomorphic to $M(X|(uv)w - (vu)w, w(uv) - w(vu), u, v, w \in X^{**})$.

Theorem 3.1 *Let $S = \{(uv)w - (vu)w, w(uv) - w(vu), u > v, u, v, w \in X^{**}\}$. Then S is a Gröbner-Shirshov basis of the algebra $M(X|(uv)w - (vu)w, w(uv) - w(vu), u, v, w \in X^{**})$.*

Proof It is clear that $Id(S)$ is the same as the ideal generated by the set $\{(uv)w - (vu)w, w(uv) - w(vu), u, v, w \in X^{**}\}$ of $M(X)$. Let $f_{123} = (u_1u_2)u_3 - (u_2u_1)u_3, g_{123} = v_1(v_2v_3) - v_1(v_3v_2), u_1 > u_2, v_2 > v_3, u_i, v_i \in X^{**}, 1 \leq i \leq 3$. Clearly, $\overline{f_{123}} = (u_1u_2)u_3$ and $\overline{g_{123}} = v_1(v_2v_3)$. Then all possible compositions in S are the following:

- (c₁) $(f_{123}, f_{456})_{(u_1|(u_4u_5)u_6)u_2}u_3$;
- (c₂) $(f_{123}, f_{456})_{(u_1u_2|(u_4u_5)u_6)}u_3$;
- (c₃) $(f_{123}, f_{456})_{(u_1u_2)u_3|(u_4u_5)u_6}$;
- (c₄) $(f_{123}, f_{456})_{((u_4u_5)u_6)u_3}, u_1u_2 = (u_4u_5)u_6$;
- (c₅) $(f_{123}, f_{456})_{(u_1u_2)u_3}, (u_1u_2)u_3 = (u_4u_5)u_6$;
- (c₆) $(f_{123}, g_{123})_{(u_1|v_1(v_2v_3)u_2)}u_3$;
- (c₇) $(f_{123}, g_{123})_{(u_1u_2|v_1(v_2v_3))}u_3$;
- (c₈) $(f_{123}, g_{123})_{(u_1u_2)u_3|v_1(v_2v_3)}$;
- (c₉) $(f_{123}, g_{123})_{(v_1(v_2v_3))u_3}, u_1u_2 = v_1(v_2v_3)$;
- (c₁₀) $(f_{123}, g_{123})_{(u_1u_2)(v_2v_3)}, u_1u_2 = v_1, u_3 = v_2v_3$;
- (c₁₁) $(g_{123}, f_{123})_{v_1|(u_1u_2)u_3}(v_2v_3)$;
- (c₁₂) $(g_{123}, f_{123})_{v_1(v_2|(u_1u_2)u_3)v_3}$;
- (c₁₃) $(g_{123}, f_{123})_{v_1(v_2v_3|(u_1u_2)u_3)}$;
- (c₁₄) $(g_{123}, f_{123})_{v_1((u_1u_2)u_3)}, v_2v_3 = (u_1u_2)u_3$;
- (c₁₅) $(g_{123}, g_{456})_{v_1|v_4(v_5v_6)}(v_2v_3)$;
- (c₁₆) $(g_{123}, g_{456})_{v_1(v_2|v_4(v_5v_6)v_3)}$;
- (c₁₇) $(g_{123}, g_{456})_{v_1(v_2v_3|v_4(v_5v_6))}$;
- (c₁₈) $(g_{123}, g_{456})_{v_1(v_4(v_5v_6))}, v_2v_3 = v_4(v_5v_6)$;
- (c₁₉) $(g_{123}, g_{456})_{v_1(v_2v_3)}, v_1(v_2v_3) = v_4(v_5v_6)$.

The above compositions in S all are trivial module S . Here, we only prove the following cases: (c₁), (c₄), (c₉), (c₁₀), (c₁₄), (c₁₈). The other cases can be proved similarly.

$$\begin{aligned} (f_{123}, f_{456})_{(u_1|(u_4u_5)u_6)u_2}u_3 &\equiv (u_2u_1|(u_4u_5)u_6)u_3 - (u'_1|(u_5u_4)u_6)u_2)u_3 \\ &\equiv (u_2u'_1|(u_5u_4)u_6)u_3 - (u'_1|(u_5u_4)u_6)u_2)u_3 \equiv 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (f_{123}, f_{456})_{((u_4 u_5) u_6) u_3}, u_1 u_2 &= (u_4 u_5) u_6 = (u_6 (u_4 u_5)) u_3 - ((u_5 u_4) u_6) u_3 \\ &\equiv (u_6 (u_5 u_4)) u_3 - ((u_5 u_4) u_6) u_3 \equiv 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (f_{123}, g_{123})_{(v_1 (v_2 v_3)) u_3}, u_1 u_2 &= v_1 (v_2 v_3) = ((v_2 v_3) v_1) u_3 - (v_1 (v_3 v_2)) u_3 \\ &\equiv ((v_3 v_2) v_1) u_3 - (v_1 (v_3 v_2)) u_3 \equiv 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (f_{123}, g_{123})_{(u_1 u_2) (v_2 v_3)}, u_1 u_2 = v_1, u_3 = v_2 v_3 &= (u_2 u_1) (v_2 v_3) - (u_1 u_2) (v_3 v_2) \\ &\equiv (u_2 u_1) (v_3 v_2) - (u_2 u_1) (v_3 v_2) = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (g_{123}, f_{123})_{v_1 ((u_1 u_2) u_3)}, v_2 v_3 &= (u_1 u_2) u_3 = v_1 (u_3 (u_1 u_2)) - v_1 ((u_2 u_1) u_3) \\ &\equiv v_1 (u_3 (u_2 u_1)) - v_1 ((u_2 u_1) u_3) \equiv 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (g_{123}, g_{456})_{v_1 (v_4 (v_5 v_6))}, v_2 v_3 &= (v_4 (v_5 v_6)) = v_1 ((v_5 v_6) v_4) - v_1 (v_4 (v_6 v_5)) \\ &\equiv v_1 ((v_6 v_5) v_4) - v_1 (v_4 (v_6 v_5)) \equiv 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore S is a Gröbner-Shirshov basis of the algebra $M(X|(uv)w - (vu)w, w(uv) - w(uv), u, v, w \in X^{**})$. \square

Definition 3.2 Each letter $x_i \in X$ is called a regular word of degree 1. Suppose that $u = vw$ is a nonassociative word of degree $m, m > 1$. Then $u = vw$ is called a regular word of degree m if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (S1) both v and w are regular words;
- (S2) if $v = v_1 v_2$, then $v_1 \leq v_2$;
- (S3) if $w = w_1 w_2$, then $w_1 \leq w_2$.

Lemma 3.3 Let $N(X)$ be the set of all regular words on X . Then $\text{Irr}(S) = N(X)$.

Proof Suppose that $u \in \text{Irr}(S)$. If $|u| = 1$, then $u = x \in N(X)$. If $|u| > 1$ and $u = vw$, then by induction $v, w \in N(X)$. If $v = v_1 v_2$, then $v_1 \leq v_2$, since $u \in \text{Irr}(S)$. If $w = w_1 w_2$, then $w_1 \leq w_2$, since $u \in \text{Irr}(S)$. Therefore $u \in N(X)$.

Suppose that $u \in N(X)$. If $|u| = 1$, then $u = x \in \text{Irr}(S)$. If $u = vw$, then v, w are regular and by induction $v, w \in \text{Irr}(S)$. If $v = v_1 v_2$, then $v_1 \leq v_2$, since $u \in N(X)$. If $w = w_1 w_2$, then $w_1 \leq w_2$, since $u \in N(X)$. Therefore $u \in \text{Irr}(S)$. \square

From Theorems 2.2, 3.1 and Lemma 3.3, the following result follows.

Theorem 3.4 The set $N(X)$ of all regular words on X forms a linear basis of the free algebra $LA(X)$.

§4. A Characterization Theorem

Let X be a well ordered set, $S(X)$ the Lie subalgebra, generated by X , of $LA(X)$ under the commutator $[f, g] = fg - gf$. Let $T = \{[x_i, x_j] | x_i > x_j, x_i, x_j \in X\}$ where $[x_i, x_j] = x_i x_j - x_j x_i$.

Lemma 5.1 *The set $X \cup T$ forms a linear basis of the Lie algebra $S(X)$.*

Proof Let $u \in X \cup T$. If $u = x_i$, then $\bar{u} = x_i$. If $u = [x_i, x_j], x_i > x_j$, then $u = x_i x_j - x_j x_i$ and thus $\bar{u} = x_i x_j$. Then we may conclude that if $u, v \in X \cup T$ and $u \neq v$, then $\bar{u} \neq \bar{v}$. Therefore the elements in $X \cup T$ are linear independent. Since $[[f, g], h] = (fg)h - (gf)h - h(fg) + h(gf) = 0 = -[h, [f, g]]$, then all the Lie words with degree ≥ 3 equal zero. Therefore, the set $X \cup T$ forms a linear basis of the Lie algebra $S(X)$. \square

Corollary 5.2 *Let $|X| > 1$. Then the Lie subalgebra $S(X)$ of $LA(X)$ is not a free Lie algebra.*

Theorem 5.3 *An element $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_s)$ of the algebra $LA(X)$ belongs to $S(X)$ if and only if $d(f) < 3$ and the relations $x_i x'_j = x'_j x_i, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ imply the equation $f(x_1 + x'_1, x_2 + x'_2, \dots, x_s + x'_s) = f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_s) + f(x'_1, x'_2, \dots, x'_s)$.*

Proof Suppose that an element $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_s)$ of the algebra $LA(X)$ belongs to $S(X)$. From Lemma 4.1, it follows that $d(f) < 3$ and it suffices to prove that if $u(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_s) \in X \cup T$, then the relations $x_i x'_j = x'_j x_i$ imply the equation $u(x_1 + x'_1, x_2 + x'_2, \dots, x_s + x'_s) = u(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_s) + u(x'_1, x'_2, \dots, x'_s)$. This holds since $d(f) < 3$ and $[x'_i, x_j] = [x_j, x'_i] = 0, x'_i, x_j, 1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

Let d_1 be an element of the algebra $LA(X)$ that does not belong to $S(X)$. If $\bar{d}_1 = x_i x_j$ where $x_i > x_j$, then let $d_2 = d_1 - [x_i, x_j]$. Clearly, d_2 is also an element of the algebra $LA(X)$ that does not belong to $S(X)$. Then after a finite number of steps of the above algorithm, we will obtain an element d_t whose leading term is u_t where $u_t = x_p x_q, x_p \leq x_q$. It's easy to see that in the expression

$$d_t(x_1 + x'_1, x_2 + x'_2, \dots, x_s + x'_s) - d_t(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_s) - d_t(x'_1, x'_2, \dots, x'_s)$$

the element $x'_q x_p$ occurs with nonzero coefficient. \square

References

- [1] A. A. Adrian, Power-associative rings, *Transactions of the American Mathematical Society*, 64 (1948), 552-593.
- [2] A. Agrachev and R. Gamkrelidze, Chronological algebras and nonstationary vector fields, *J. Sov. Math.*, 17 (1981), 1650-1675.
- [3] M. J. H. AL-Kaabi, Monomial bases for free pre-Lie algebras, *Séminaire Lotharingien de Combinatoire*, 17 (2014), Article B71b.
- [4] G.M. Bergman, The diamond lemma for ring theory, *Adv. in Math.*, 29 (1978), 178-218.
- [5] L.A. Bokut, Imbeddings into simple associative algebras, *Algebra i Logika*, 15 (1976), 117-142.

- [6] L. A. Bokut and Y. Q. Chen, Gröbner-Shirshov bases for Lie algebras: after A. I. Shirshov, *Southeast Asian Bull. Math.*, 31 (2007), 1057-1076.
- [7] B. Buchberger, An algorithmical criteria for the solvability of algebraic systems of equations (in German), *Aequationes Math.*, 4 (1970), 374-383.
- [8] D. Burde, Left-symmetric algebras, or pre-Lie algebras in geometry and physics, *Central European J. of Mathematics*, 4 (3) (2006), 323-357.
- [9] A. Cayley, On the theory of analitical forms called trees, *Phil. Mag.*, 13 (1857), 19-30.
- [10] F. Chapoton and M. Livernet, Pre-Lie Algebras and the Rooted Trees Operad, *International Mathematics Research Notices*, 8 (2001), 395-408.
- [11] Y. Q. Chen and Y. Li, Some remarks on the Akivis algebras and the pre-Lie algebras, *Czechoslovak Mathematical Journal* 61 (136) (2011), 707-720.
- [12] Y.Q. Chen and Q.H. Mo, A note on Artin-Markov normal form theorem for braid groups, *Southeast Asian Bull. Math.*, 33 (2009), 403-419.
- [13] Y.Q. Chen and J.J. Qiu, Groebner-Shirshov basis for free product of algebras and beyond, *Southeast Asian Bull. Math.*, 30 (2006), 811-826.
- [14] A. Dzhumadil'daev and C. Löfwall, Trees, free right-symmetric algebras, free Novikov algebras and identities, *Homology, Homotopy and Applications*, 4 (2) (2002), 165-190.
- [15] K. O. Friedrichs, Mathematical aspects of the quantum theory of fields, V. *Comm. Pure Appl. Math.*, 6 (1953), 1-72.
- [16] H. Hironaka, Resolution of singularities of an algebraic variety over a field if characteristic zero, I, II, *Ann. of Math.*, 79 (1964), 109-203, 205-326.
- [17] R. C. Lyndon, A theorem of Friedrichs, *Michigan Math. J.*, 3 (1) (1955), 27-29.
- [18] W. Magnus, On the exponential solution of differential equations for a linear operator, *Comm. Pure Appl. Math.*, 7 (1954), 649-673.
- [19] M. Markl, Lie elements in pre-Lie algebras, trees and cohomology operations, *Journal of Lie Theory*, 17 (2007), 241-261.
- [20] D. Segal, Free left-symmetric algebras and an analogue of the Poincaré-Birkhoff-Witt Theorem, *J. Algebra*, 164 (1994), 750-772.
- [21] A. I. Shirshov, On free Lie rings, *Sibirsk. Mat. Sb.*, 45 (1958), 113-122.
- [22] A.I. Shirshov, Some algorithmic problem for ε -algebras, *Sibirsk. Mat. Z.*, 3 (1962), 132-137.
- [23] A.I. Shirshov, Some algorithmic problem for Lie algebras, *Sibirsk. Mat. Z.*, 3 (1962), 292-296 (in Russian); English translation in *SIGSAM Bull.*, 33(2) (1999), 3-6.
- [24] Selected Works of A. I. Shirshov, Eds. L. A. Bokut, V. Latyshev, I. Shestakov, E. Zelmanov, Trs. M. Bremner, M. Kochetov, Birkhäuser, Basel, Boston, Berlin, (2009).
- [25] E. A. Vasil'eva and A. A. Mikhalev, Free left-symmetric superalgebras, *Fundamental and Applied Mathematics*, 2 (1996), 611-613.